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ATTITUDES OF TEACHERS TO ICT USAGE IN SECONDARY SCHOOL MANAGEMENT IN AWKA SOUTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ANAMBRA STATE

By

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Abstract

The study examined attitudes of teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 604 teachers (60 males and 544 females) from the 19 public secondary schools in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. All the 604 teachers were used for the study due to relatively manageable size of the population. A researcher-developed instrument titled "Attitudes of Teachers to Information and Communication Technology Usage in School Management Questionnaire (ATICTUSMQ)" was used for data collection. The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts from Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. The internal consistency of the instruments was determined using Cronbach Alpha which yielded reliability value of 0.79. The instruments were administered by the researcher with the help of three research assistants who are secondary school teachers in Anambra State. A total of 604 copies of the questionnaires were distributed and 593 were properly filled and successfully retrieved indicating 98% return rate. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The findings of the study revealed that teachers have high self-efficacy and willingness to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Ministry of Education should develop policy that is geared towards improving self-efficacy of teachers to ICT usage in school management.

Keywords:

Attitudes, Teachers, ICT Usage, School Management, Self-Efficacy, Willingness

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Introduction

Education plays a pivotal role in the growth and development of any nation. It also serves as a means through which individuals strive to improve themselves and their surroundings. Education is an essential instrument for driving national progress and a transformative process that enables individuals to acquire knowledge and essential skills for their personal development (Iwuanyanwu & Uwadiogwu, 2019). One of the important levels of education is secondary schools.

Secondary education is the education that students get after successfully completing nine years of basic education. The broad aims of secondary education in Nigeria are to prepare individuals for meaningful life in society and for further education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). The realization of the goals of secondary education could be influenced by school management.

School management involves leading the learning institution towards development through optimum use of human, material and financial resources to achieve predetermined educational objectives (Agobua et al., 2019). School management is a continuous process of applying policies and utilizing the available resources to attain set educational goals. School management is described by Awolola (2017) as the act of running the affairs of an institute efficiently and effectively. Management in school entails planning, directing, controlling and organizing the institution by making effective use of human and material resources to accomplish a set objective. The primary focus in school management is the improvement of teaching and learning and all the activities of the school. School management aims at bringing members of staff of the school, students, head-teacher, and other stakeholders in education to work together as a team in order to achieve the desired goals and objectives of the school.

There are managerial problems in secondary schools in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. Anyanwu, Oparaji and Obilor (2024) noted that there are uncomfortable levels of unruly behaviours of the students in the class and on the secondary school premises in Anambra State. It seems that some students are fond of coming late to school, running around the class, withdrawing from instructional activities, making noise and damaging furniture of the classroom in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Okeke (2021) noted that students exhibit indiscipline behaviour such as persist lateness to classes, truancy, fighting, loitering during classes, examination malpractices, absenteeism, breach of school's rules and regulation in secondary schools in Anambra State. Akudo and Nweke (2024) noted that some secondary schools in Anambra State, there seems to be cases of chairs and tables littered all around the school premises, broken windows and doors, dilapidated buildings and exposed electrical fittings in classroom. Effective management of secondary schools can be greatly influenced by the usage of Information and Communication Technology (ICT).

ICT is referred to the convergence of audio-visual and telephone networks with computer networks through a single cabling or link system. There are significant economic incentives to unify the telephone network and the computer network into a single integrated system, which includes cabling, signal distribution, and management. Ikegbusi (2016) further elaborated that ICT serves as an umbrella term encompassing various communication devices, such as radio, television, cell phones, computer and network hardware, satellite systems, and more. It also includes the various services and appliances associated with these devices, like video conferencing and distance learning. Ikegbusi further emphasized that ICT is a broad and evolving field that encompasses any product capable of electronically storing, retrieving, manipulating, transmitting, or receiving information in digital form. This includes personal computers, smartphones, digital television, email, and even robots.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) usage can significantly enhance education by revolutionizing the learning process and fostering a more conducive educational environment. Through the integration of computers, tablets, data displays, interactive electronic boards, and other technological tools, information can be effectively communicated to students (Ajani, 2016). ICT usage in secondary school management makes it easier to create a conducive learning environment and allows for the smooth transmission of knowledge, which benefits both teachers and students by broadening their educational horizons (Venkateswar et al., 2020). One of the primary goals of teaching using ICT is to improve the teaching abilities of educators at all levels. Teachers must be well prepared in order to get a solid grasp of the academic and practical elements of ICT use (Ramadass & Shah, 2022). This understanding enables teachers to solve a variety of classroom difficulties, including as managing student diversity and heterogeneity. In the context of this study, ICT usage refers to the utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools, resources, and applications to facilitate various tasks, activities, and processes in different domains such as education, business, healthcare, government, and daily life. However, the use of ICT in the teaching and learning process is dependent on teachers' attitude towards it.

Attitude of teachers is the way a teacher reason or acts and most of the times can either make or mar teachers' performance while carrying out their tasks and responsibilities. Ikwuka, Onyali, Olugbemi, Etodike, Igbokwe and Adigwe (2020) described attitude as the behavioural and psychological disposition of a teacher towards utilization of ICT in teaching and learning process in an educational setting. It had been established by scholars such as Shittu and Oanite (2015) that teachers' attitudes highly influence students' interest in learning. The attitude of teachers refers to the way they perceive and think which may lead to the actions they take related to their teaching practices in the classroom. It is a teacher characteristic and component of teacher personality and it can impact their interactions with students and the overall classroom environment (Ramadass & Shah, 2022). Effective teacher attitudes often include genuine caring and kindness, willingness to share responsibility, sensitivity to students' diversity, motivation to provide meaningful learning experiences, and enthusiasm for stimulating students' creativity (Hadriana, 2019). In the context of this study, attitude of teachers is defined as teachers' mindset, demeanor and approach towards their profession, students, and the educational process as a whole.

Attitude of teachers towards the use of ICT may be positive or negative. Positive attitudes could make teachers to integrate ICT in school management, while negative attitude could discourage them from utilizing technological devices in school management. There are some dimensions of teachers' attitudes toward ICT usage in school management. The dimensions to evaluate the teachers' attitude towards the usage of ICT in school system are self-efficacy, anxiety, avoidance, confidence, enthusiasm and liking (Bariu & Chun, 2022). Similarly, Semerci and Aydın (2018) noted that teachers' attitude toward ICT use in education could be determined using ICT willingness and ICT anxiety. This study focused on self-efficacy, anxiety, willingness and enthusiasm.

Self-efficacy is the belief in one's capability to effectively carry out an activity. According to Abosede, Idris and Wilfred-Bonse (2023), self-efficacy is a belief in one's ability to execute specific tasks and achieve desired outcomes. Teachers' self-efficacy in the use of ICT is shape their attitude towards applying them in executing their duties. Hortelano, Ramos, Gutierrez and Catapang (2021) described self-efficacy as the judgment of one's capability to use ICT facilities effective teaching and management tools in classrooms. Sabic, Baranovic and Rogosic (2022) asserted that teachers' self-efficacy has a powerful influence on their behaviour towards the use of ICT in schools. Furthermore, Sabic et al stressed that it determines whether the teachers will use ICT, in what way, to what extent

and how successful they will use ICT for instructional and managerial purposes in schools. Teachers with high self-efficacy are likely to feel confident of using ICT to communicate and manage classroom and school affairs.

ICT willingness is the state of being ready to integrate digital devices in discharging one's duties. It is being happy and prepared to use ICT to complete a given task. Ayot, Ogembo and Ondigi (2015) noted that teachers' willingness to use ICT tools such as computers in classroom is a factor of their attitude towards use of such tools and the importance that they attach to the use of the tools in classroom teaching. Teachers are required to be mentally and physically willing to use ICT to meet the dynamic demand of school management. Semerci and Aydın (2018) maintained that teachers could be willing to use ICT when they believe that it is a fruitful means for planning lesson, making teaching easier and increasing students' success in class for attainment of set educational objectives.

Gender refers to the social and cultural roles, behaviours, expectations, and characteristics that a society believes suitable for people depending on their biological sex (Ikwuka et al., 2020). Gender differs from biological sex, which relates to physical and genetic distinctions between men and women (Youngkyun et al., 2017). Gender identity and expression include masculinity, femininity, and many non-binary and gender-diverse identities. It is a broad and nuanced idea that differs throughout cultures and countries. Gender stereotypes, such as the notion that males are more tech-savvy or confident with ICT than females, are common in society (Ogirima et al., 2017). Also, Adegoke, Akano and Owolabi (2019) noted there was gender difference in teachers' use of ICT. These preconceptions might have an impact on teachers' confidence and enthusiasm to use ICT technologies.

The literature on academic members of staff reveals varying perspectives on gender differences in attitudes toward ICT use, and the research provides inconclusive results. On one hand, certain studies have concluded that gender-based disparities do not exist (Amie-Ogan&Ubani, 2020; Fomsi & Orduah, 2017). For instance, when examining how teachers perceive the use of ICT in secondary schools in Edo State, Nigeria, Otemuyiwa and Attah (2020) found that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers on their perception of the use of ICT. They attribute this to the normalization of ICT use in today's world. This finding aligns with the results of a survey conducted in India by Bhat and Bashir (2018), which indicated that there are no significant distinctions between male and female university teachers regarding their attitudes toward ICT. In this case, both male and female teachers exhibited similar attitudes toward ICT use. These studies suggest that gender may not be a decisive factor in determining teachers' attitudes towards ICT in the academic context.

It appears that there is a problem of utilizing ICT facilities by teachers in secondary schools in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. To buttress this, Ogbunode, Obi and Nwankwo (2021) noted that the available ICT facilities are hardly properly utilized towards managing schools due to lack of qualified and experienced teachers to operate them in secondary schools in Anambra State. The underutilization of ICT facilities tends to contribute to managerial problems in secondary schools in Anambra State. Nwafor and Egboka (2020) observed that some schools are bedeviled with incidences of indiscipline among staff and students, poor decision making, examination malpractice, improper planning, poor implementation and shortage of relevant facilities which may indicate ineffective management of secondary schools in Anambra State. Also, Okeke and Ikediugwu (2021) maintained that it is worrisome that records keeping remain manually-based and unorganized which makes it difficult to keep track of managerial and classroom activities such as school attendance, monitoring of

examinations and planning of instructional programmes in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Abosedo, Idris and Wilfred-Bonse (2023) noted that teachers still exhibit considerable technology phobia in secondary schools in Nigeria. It is against this background that this study was undertaken to the attitudes of teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

The management of secondary school is a very important aspect of ensuring the realization of goals of the National Policy on Education. However, it seems that teachers are yet to make desirable contributions towards the management of secondary schools in Awka South Local Government, Anambra State. Teachers appear to find it difficult to manage the daily school attendance of students, the available facilities in classroom and plan instructional activities in secondary schools in Awka South Local Government, Anambra State. Some students tend to loiter in school premises during instruction, engage in examination malpractices, violate school rule and regulations and display other forms of misconduct in secondary schools in Awka South LGA.

Some teachers tend to manually keep data of students and carry out some managerial tasks that could easily be done using ICT facilities in secondary schools in Awka South Local Government, Anambra State. Also, some teachers appear to be conversant with conventional method of managing school affairs which probably affect their attitude towards ICT usage. Consequently, it appears that there is shortage of information for planning and decisions making in secondary schools in Awka South Local Government, Anambra State. These problems prompted the investigation of attitudes of teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine attitudes of teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. find out the self-efficacy of male and female teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State.
2. determine the willingness of male and female teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the self-efficacy of male and female teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State?
2. What is the willingness of male and female teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State?

METHODS

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The study was carried out in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State. The choice of the area for the study is informed by the fact that the students' attendance, data and instructional activities are poorly managed by teachers in secondary schools in Awka South LGA. The population of the study comprised 604 teachers (60 males and 544 females) from the 19 public secondary schools in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. There was no sampling since the entire population is relatively small and manageable.

Therefore, the researcher applied census sampling technique in selecting all 604 public secondary school teachers in Awka South LGA for the study.

A researcher-developed instrument titled “Attitudes of Teachers to Information and Communication Technology Usage in School Management Questionnaire (ATICTUSMQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument was structured by the researcher based on literature review and suggestions of experts. The instrument had two sections- A and B. Section A contains three items on respondents’ background information covering respondents’ gender. Section B had two clusters A and B which contained 20 items on attitude of teachers to ICT usage.

Cluster A had 10 items on self-efficacy of teachers to ICT usage in school management and Cluster B had 10 items on willingness of teachers to ICT usage in school management. The instrument was structured on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The face validation of the instrument was determined by three experts in the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha method which yielded coefficient of 0.79 and 0.78 respectively and overall coefficient was 0.79.

Data was collected by the researcher with the help of three research assistants who are teachers in secondary schools. The research assistants were briefed by the researcher on the content and mode of the instruments administration. A total of 604 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 593 were properly filled and successfully retrieved indicating 98% return rate. At the end of the exercise, copies of the questionnaire properly filled and successfully retrieved were used for data analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The decision criteria on the research questions are that any item with a mean score equal or above 2.50 indicated agreement, while the item with a mean score below 2.50 indicated disagreement.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the self-efficacy of teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on the Self-Efficacy of Teachers to ICT Usage in Secondary School Management

S/ N	ITEMS	Male Teachers (n =57)			Female Teachers (n=536)		
		x	SD	Remark	x	SD	Remark
1	Feel confident that I can effectively use electronic devices in managing the activities of students in classroom	2.68	1.03	Agree	2.71	1.08	Agree
2	Possess the competency to organise classroom activities using computer	2.61	1.07	Agree	2.59	1.00	Agree
3	Believe that I have mastered the techniques to plan activities using computer	2.71	1.10	Agree	2.82	0.98	Agree
4	Show good mastery of using the right software in managing records of students	2.47	1.00	Disagree	2.44	1.01	Disagree
5	Exhibit ability to use electronic devices in managing classroom activities	2.73	1.11	Agree	2.69	0.97	Agree
6	Feel confident that I can learn to use new ICT tools independently in performing managing tasks	2.55	1.08	Agree	2.76	1.05	Agree
7	Think I possess the knowledge of the right digital device to use in managing each activity in the	2.64	1.12	Agree	2.65	1.01	Agree

8	classroom Feel self-confident of using ICT devices to source required information to aid classroom management	2.70	1.04	Agree	2.61	1.03	Agree
9	Am capable of applying ICT tools in exchanging information with parents about their children	2.65	1.01	Agree	2.71	1.12	Agree
10	Think that I have the ability report students progress to school management using technological devices	2.65	0.94	Agree	2.61	1.00	Agree
Cluster Mean		2.64	1.05	Agree	2.66	1.03	Agree

Data analysis as shown in Table 1 revealed that the mean scores of male and female teachers for all items 2 with exception of item 4 are above 2.50 indicating agreement with the items as their efficacy to ICT usage in secondary school management. The cluster standard scores which stood at 1.05 and 1.03 for male and female teachers respectively indicated similarity in their responses amongst each cluster. The clusters mean of 2.58 and 2.65 obtained by male and female teachers which are above the cut off mean score of 2.50 indicated teachers have high efficacy in ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State/

Research Question 2: What is the willingness of teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on the Willingness of Teachers to ICT Usage in Secondary School Management

S/ N	ITEMS	Male Teachers (n =57)			Female Teachers (n=536)		
		x	SD	Remark	x	SD	Remark
11	Prepared to manage the daily attendance of students using Roll Call App	2.54	1.03	Agree	2.61	1.04	Agree
12	Eager to store the records of students in continuous assessment using computer	2.81	1.02	Agree	2.74	1.07	Agree
13	Ready to manage examination questions with easy using Microsoft Excel	2.61	1.10	Agree	2.67	0.93	Agree
14	Keen to facilitate class registration process of students using computer	2.71	1.06	Agree	2.66	1.09	Agree
15	Ready to integrate computer equipment in managing classroom discipline	2.53	1.10	Agree	2.59	1.01	Agree
16	Disposed to disseminate vital information in school using WhatsApp	2.70	1.05	Agree	2.65	1.00	Agree
17	Prepared to make classroom announcements for students with Microsoft Word	2.68	1.09	Agree	2.61	1.10	Agree
18	Prepared progress reports of students using computer	2.59	0.94	Agree	2.67	0.96	Agree
19	Greatly ready to manage my lesson note using computer	2.55	1.01	Agree	2.72	1.02	Agree
20	Interested in using ICT in curriculum management	2.61	1.00	Agree	2.70	1.06	Agree
Cluster Mean		2.63	1.04	Agree	2.66	1.03	Agree

Table 2 revealed that the mean scores of male and female teachers for all items are above 2.50 indicating agreement with the items as their willingness to ICT usage in secondary school management. The cluster standard scores which stood at 1.04 and 1.03 for male and female teachers

respectively indicated similarity in their responses amongst each cluster. The clusters mean of 2.63 and 2.66 obtained by male and female teachers which are above the cut off mean score of 2.50 indicated teachers show high willingness to ICT usage in secondary school management based on gender in Awka South LGA of Anambra State.

Discussion of the Findings

The finding of the study revealed that teachers have high self-efficacy to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. This is in line with the finding of Hortelano, Ramos, Gutierrez and Catapang (2021) which indicated that teachers have high level of self-efficacy in the use of the ICT facilities in schools. This also supported the finding of Abosede, Idris and Wilfred-Bonse (2023) which revealed that majority of teachers have high self-efficacy in the use of ICT in schools. This disagreed with the finding of Koross (2024) who indicated that teachers have low self-efficacy in using ICT in secondary schools. This disagreement with the finding could be explained by difference in the geographical location. This finding probably explained that teachers have belief in their abilities to perform managerial tasks using ICT. It revealed that teachers have high confidence, competency and the belief in the use of ICT in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. Teachers can effectively use ICT to manage classroom activities. The self-efficacy of male and female teachers drives their motivation to use ICT in managing their daily activities in secondary schools.

It was revealed that teachers exhibited high willingness to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. This is in disagreement with the finding of Ayot, Ogembo and Ondigi (2015) which showed that female teachers recorded a higher level of willingness to integrate as compared to their male counterparts. The disagreement could be attributed to difference in time span. This finding probably indicated that teachers are always ready and prepared to use ICT in school management. Teachers are very willing to manage records, daily attendance, prepare academic progress reports and facilitate class registration of students using ICT in secondary schools in Awka South LGA of Anambra State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that teachers have positive attitude towards the use of ICT in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. Male and female teachers have high self-efficacy and willingness towards the use of ICT in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Ministry of Education should develop policy that is geared towards improving self-efficacy of teachers to ICT usage in school management.
2. Ministry of Education should embark on regular unscheduled visit to schools to ensure continuous willingness of male and female teachers to use ICT in managing classroom affairs.

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